

IMPROVING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF LOCAL PRODUCTS WITH MOTION GRAPHIC VIDEOS: A PROMOTIONAL STUDY OF RAYA HONEY SIBETAN

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Abstract: *This article aims to improve the competitiveness of local products of Raya Honey Sibetan, an MSME in Bali, through motion graphic videos as promotional media. It was found that the low participation of teenagers in buying Raya Honey Sibetan honey products was due to the lack of information and ineffective promotion. Therefore, the Design Thinking approach was used in the process of designing an attractive and informative motion graphic video for the target audience of teenagers aged 18-22 years. This approach includes Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Testing stages, to understand the needs of the audience, develop creative ideas, create video prototypes, and test the feasibility of the video. The results show that this motion graphic video is able to increase teenagers' awareness and interest in honey products, with the test results obtaining a feasibility level of 93.28% which is categorized as "Very Good." This motion graphic video is expected to be an effective promotional media to expand market reach and increase the competitiveness of local products in the digital marketing era.*

Keywords: *motion graphic, promotional media, honey.*

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1. Introduction

MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises) have a significant role in economic recovery in Indonesia. MSMEs contribute to increasing employment and accelerating regional economic development. However, along with increasing business competition, innovative and effective marketing strategies are needed so that MSMEs can survive and thrive (Wasik et al., 2023).

Raya Honey Sibetan is one of the MSMEs located in Karangasem Regency, Bali. The business is engaged in beekeeping and produces pure honey from Trigona, Apis Cerana, and Apis Dorsata bees. Despite offering high-quality honey products, Raya Honey Sibetan faces the challenge of low youth participation in purchasing its products. This low participation is due to the lack of information about Raya Honey Sibetan's honey products and the lack of understanding of the benefits of honey. Communication limitations are a challenge for the owner of this MSME, as he uses sign language to communicate. This causes the delivery of product information and the benefits of Raya Honey Sibetan honey to potential consumers to be less than optimal, especially to attract teenagers. In addition, the promotional methods currently used are still limited and less effective in reaching a wider audience,

especially teenagers who tend to consume more interactive digital and visual content.

In terms of modern marketing, digital media plays an important role in introducing products to consumers. One form of promotion that is currently popular and effective is motion graphic video. Motion graphic videos can convey messages visually and dynamically, which is more attractive to audiences, especially teenagers (Pakpahan & Zpalanzani Mansoor, 2022). In addition, the dissemination of these videos through social media such as Instagram and Youtube also allows a wider audience to reach. Therefore, motion graphic videos as promotional media are expected to help Raya Honey Sibetan in increasing awareness and interest of teenagers in the honey products they offer (Puspitarini & Nuraeni, 2019).

This article integrates a visual communication design approach through motion graphic videos as a more relevant solution for teenage audiences. Video motion graphics are an innovation in visual communication that combines graphic elements, text, illustrations, and animations to create dynamic and visually appealing promotional content. In the context of marketing communication theory, visual media such as motion graphic videos can increase the effectiveness of message delivery because they

utilize a combination of moving images, text, and audio to attract audience attention, build brand image, and increase consumer understanding and engagement (Rosalia & Hidajat, 2022; Sari, 2019).

Unlike conventional promotional methods that only use print media or oral promotions, this article conducts a more efficient promotional strategy, namely through motion graphic content that is widely accessible and has viral potential. This article lies not only in the utilization of motion graphic technology as a promotional medium but also in the marketing strategy approach tailored to teenagers' media preferences, combining visual communication theory with digital marketing applications.

2. Research Method

This article uses the Design Thinking approach to design and develop promotional media in the form of motion graphic videos for Raya Honey Sibetan MSMEs. Design Thinking was chosen because this approach is human-centered, allowing researchers to deeply understand user needs and desires and produce creative and relevant solutions (Sari et al., 2020; Soedewi, 2022). The method consists of five main stages: Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test (Resmadi, 2022; Setiawan et al., 2022). The following is a detailed explanation of each stage:

Figure 1. Design Thinking

[Source: Syahrul, 2019]

1) Empathize

The author focuses on understanding the needs, limitations, and desires of business owners and consumers. Direct observation of the production and marketing process, in-depth interviews with business owners, and production to consumers are carried out to collect the necessary data.

2) Define

Once the data was collected, the author analyzed the findings to define the problem more specifically. The main problems identified included communication barriers due to the use of sign language, promotion limited to print media, and low awareness of Raya Honey Sibetan honey products among teenage consumers.

3) Ideate

The author develops a variety of creative ideas to address the problems that have been defined, Brainstroming generates innovative promotional media concepts, such as video

dissemination through social media platforms that are popular among teenagers.

4) Prototype

Based on the ideas generated, the author creates a motion graphic video prototype. This prototype was designed by utilizing the principles of visual communication design to ensure that the message conveyed can be well understood by the target audience.

5) Test

The final stage is to test the prototype to the target audience to gather feedback and assess the effectiveness of the motion graphic video as a promotional medium. The test was conducted through video playback to the target audience consisting of local consumers and teenagers, as well as collecting feedback through questionnaires.

The framework for designing a promotional motion graphics video for Raya Honey Sibetan using the design thinking method can be seen in the chart in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Framework for the creation of Raya Honey Sibetan motion graphic video

[Source: Author's Documentation]

The framework for the creation of Raya Honey Sibetan motion graphic video using the Design Thinking approach starts from the background of the problem, namely the limited communication and promotion of Raya Honey Sibetan UMKM to teenagers. Through the Empathize stage, observations, interviews, and questionnaires are conducted to understand audience kebitihan. The Define stage defines the main problems, namely the limited use of sign language by business voters, the lack of promotion, and the low awareness of adolescents of honey products, then, at the Ideate stage, the idea of making a motion graphic video as a promotional media is generated. A video prototype with 1920x1080 pixel specifications was made in the Prototype stage, which was then tested on 100 teenagers aged 18-22 years in Denpasar in the Testing stage to assess its effectiveness. Conclusions and suggestions are compiled based on the test results to determine the feasibility of motion graphic videos as effective promotional media for the target audience.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Emphatize

In the early stages of designing motion graphic videos, the target audience was determined, namely to teenagers aged 18-22 years in

Denpasar City, a total of 100 people. Then observations were made of the target audience by asking questions through a questionnaire to find out the outline of the audience's understanding of Raya Honey Sibetan honey. From the results of the questionnaire, 97% of the audience stated that they were interested in knowing more about the various types of honey available, 94% of the audience stated that they had never heard or known about Raya Honey Sibetan, 96% of the audience stated that they did not know the product of Raya Honey Sibetan, and 98% of the audience stated that they did not know the content and benefits of consuming Raya Honey Sibetan products.

Next, the author conducted observations and observations at Raya Honey Sibetan through direct visits. From this direct visit, the author obtained data that this farm has a well-maintained physical condition and is supported by an environment suitable for beekeeping. There are bee colonies placed in neatly arranged hives, as well as tools and other equipment such as protective clothing and sterilization equipment. In addition, the cleanliness of the farm and security are well taken care of. These observations provided a deeper understanding of the beekeeping conditions and production processes at Raya Honey Sibetan.

Figure 3. Honeycombs in Raya Honey Sibetan

[Source: Author's Documentation]

3.2 Define

In this second stage, the authors collected data about Raya Honey Sibetan by direct observation of the Raya Honey Sibetan farm itself supported by interviews with the owner and conducting literature studies. Interviews were conducted with the owner of Raya Honey Sibetan Mr. I Kadek Swanjaya to obtain data directly regarding important aspects related to the business and products produced by Raya Honey Sibetan. From the results of interviews with Mr. I Kadek Swanjaya, the owner of Raya Honey Sibetan who is assisted by sign language to translate verbal communication into sign language and vice versa, obtained information about the background of the Company, product types, production processes, consumption methods, content and benefits of Raya Honey Sibetan honey. He explained that Raya Honey Sibetan is mostly visited by consumers from Karangasem, Bali and surrounding areas. Meanwhile, consumers from outside the area generally consist of adults and the elderly. He wishes to expand the market by reaching consumers outside the area who have not previously been reached. But until now, Raya Honey Sibetan only uses conventional promotional media and does not yet have digital promotional media in its promotion.

3.3 Ideate

This third stage is to collect as many ideas as possible and process them into the right media. Motion graphic videos make the right media as supporting promotional media to introduce Raya Honey Sibetan and the honey products produced. Therefore, it is necessary to have digital promotional media in the form of motion graphic videos as supporting media to introduce Raya Honey Sibetan and the products produced. With motion graphics, information about honey products and their advantages can be conveyed more easily. In addition, motion graphic promotional media can be disseminated through online social media platforms and has the advantage of wider reach.

The motion graphic video will be designed by combining elements such as text, illustrations, and images creatively in the form of a video to convey messages. The elements are arranged in a dynamic layout with movement, transitions, and visual effects that combine and unify the elements. Images are used as a visual background to

convey the message more concretely. Illustrations are used to reinforce the message or story. Text is used to convey information or messages. The use of bright colors such as yellow, orange, red and green, as well as typography that uses a modern and easy-to-read sans serif typeface. The message in this motion graphic aims to introduce and promote honey products from Raya Hiney Sibetan. The message uses a formal art language style and is organized in a persuasive manner to invite the audience to buy the honey product.

3.4 Prototype

The motion graphic video will select and arrange the elements of illustration, typography, color, sound, and scenario. The illustrations used are illustrations with simple designs to create visual elements that create visual effects. This visual effect is used to clarify the message and attract attention in the motion graphic video.

Figure 4. Virus Illustration

[Source: Author's Documentation]

The colors used are bright colors, namely yellow, orange, red and green. Visually, the colors yellow, orange, red and green are prominent and striking, thus attracting the audience's attention. In addition, some colors have appropriate associations with honey products.

Figure 5. Color palette

[Source: Author's Documentation]

Then the typography used is a typography with a sans serif typeface, namely the Montserrat Font. The Montserrat font has a complete family of letters with various variants and weights that can meet different design needs, and the clean, simple, and undecorated letterforms help ensure the clarity of the text for easy reading by the audience.

Figure 6. Montserrat font

[Source: Author's Documentation]

The sounds used include narration, sound effects and backsound. The narration will be delivered by a man by conveying

informational and persuasive messages listed on the storyboard. Meanwhile, the sound effects used are sneezing sounds to increase the attractiveness and effectiveness of the message conveyed. In addition, the backsound used is happy music, a type of music that is energetic, has a strong rhythm, and a fast tempo to create a dynamic and energetic atmosphere.

Synopsis for the motion graphic video to convey a message about health problems and their solutions through honey products. In the video, information about Raya Honey Sibetan is presented, including product content, product benefits, product variants, product advantages, and how to order the product. Every word or sentence used contains a persuasive message that aims to introduce and invite audiences to buy honey products offered by Raya Honey Sibetan.

3.5 Testing

Testing of the public, especially the target audience, was carried out to evaluate the material content and visual appearance of the motion graphic video as a promotional media for Raya Honey Sibetan. This was done through collecting opinions using a questionnaire available in the form of a google form containing a link to the final project video. The number of respondents involved was 100 teenagers aged 18-22 years in Denpasar City. The assessment instrument used was a Likert Scale consisting of 5 statements. The assessment of the target audience is then processed to obtain a percentage of the feasibility of this promotional media. Analysis of the test results on the target audience can be seen as follows:

Table 1. Community Testing Results

No.	Statement	Answer	Number	Weight	Result
1	The information conveyed in the motion graphic video can be clearly understood	SS	65	5	325
		S	34	4	136
		N	1	3	3
		TS	0	2	0
		STS	0	1	0
Total Score					464
Index (%) = Total Score/Y x 100					
= 464/500 x 100					
= 92,8% (Strongly Agree)					
No.	Statement	Answer	Number	Weight	Result
2	The visual display in the motion graphic video is clear and comfortable to look at	SS	69	5	345
		S	29	4	116
		N	2	3	6
		TS	0	2	0
		STS	0	1	0
Total Score					467
Index (%) = Total Score /Y x 100					
= 467/500 x 100					
= 93,4% (Strongly Agree)					

No.	Statement	Answer	Number	Weight	Result
3	The audio in the motion graphic video is clear and comfortable to listen to	SS	67	5	335
		S	31	4	124
		N	2	3	6
		TS	0	2	0
		STS	0	1	0
Total Score					465
Index (%) = Total Score/Y x 100					
= 465/500 x 100					
= 93% (Strongly Agree)					
No.	Statement	Answer	Number	Weight	Result
4	Motion graphic videos attract attention and generate your interest to find out more about Raya Honey Sibetan products	SS	57	5	285
		S	43	4	172
		N	0	3	0
		TS	0	2	0
		STS	0	1	0
Total Score					457
Index (%) = Total Score/Y x 100					
= 457/500 x 100					
= 91,4% (Strongly Agree)					
No.	Statement	Answer	Number	Weight	Result
5	Motion graphic video as a promotional media for Raya Honey Sibetan is feasible to be published	SS	79	5	395
		S	21	4	84
		N	0	3	0
		TS	0	2	0
		STS	0	1	0
Total Score					479
Index (%) = Total Score/Y x 100					
= 479/500 x 100					
= 95,8% (Strongly Agree)					

[Source: Author's Documentation]

$$\text{Respondent Percentage} = \frac{\text{total score}}{y} \times 100$$

$$\text{Respondent Percentage} = \frac{2,332}{2,500} \times 100$$

= 93,28% (very good)

The motion graphic video as a promotional media for Raya Honey Sibetan received positive responses from various aspects of the assessment. With a total percentage of 93.28%, this video is categorized as "Very Good" in the effectiveness of information delivery, visual appearance, and appeal to the teenage target audience. This level of feasibility indicates that the designed promotional media is able to achieve marketing objectives, namely increasing teenagers' awareness and interest in Raya Honey Sibetan honey products, as well as contributing to the development of effective interactive visual media-based marketing strategies.

3.6 Media Outcome

Here is the final look of the motion graphic video that has been made:

Figure 7. Visualization Result of Video Motion Graphic Raya Honey Sibetan.

[Source: Author's Documentation]

3. Conclusion

The use of motion graphic videos as promotional media for Raya Honey Sibetan MSMEs has proven to be effective in increasing the attractiveness and awareness of teenage consumers of honey products. Through the Design Thinking approach, this research successfully designed and developed a promotional video prototype that is attractive and informative, and in accordance with the preferences of teenage audiences aged 18-22 years. The test results showed that the motion graphic video received a positive response with a feasibility level of 93.28%, which is included in the "Very Good" category in terms of information delivery, visual appearance, and audience appeal. This motion graphic video can become an effective promotional tool and has the potential to expand the market reach of local products such as Raya Honey Sibetan honey, as well as contribute to a visual media-based marketing strategy that can be widely accessed through social media platforms.

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